

PREPARATION OF EMULSIONS FROM OIL EXTRACTS AND EVALUATION OF QUALITY INDICATORS

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It consists in obtaining stable emulsions from oil extracts in the presence of various surfactants..

ABSTRACT

Emulsions obtained by adding various surfactants to oil extracts are of great practical importance. Compared to oil extracts, the absorption of emulsions is higher, and the biologically active substances contained in the extract are easier to penetrate into the body, and their dystrophic form of periodontitis) and upper respiratory tract [1-4]. Oil extracts based on medicinal plants have a special place in this field. At the moment, oil extracts have a number of advantages (naturalness, simple technology, effective effect, harmlessness) that the demand for such drugs is high. At the moment, the amount of flavonoid glycosides and quercetin is low compared to alcohol extraction and tincture due to low oil solubility [5]. Bitter almond oil obtained by cold pressing method is widely used in folk medicine [6-9]. It contains vitamins A, E, F, D, linoleic and oleic acids from unsaturated fatty acids [10]. This oil is recommended for skin rejuvenation, moisturizing, and wrinkle removal in body, foot skin, face and hair care. It increases the porosity of the skin and has an anti-inflammatory effect on the skin [11-13]. Regular use of almond oil rejuvenates the facial skin and protects it from the sun's rays.

Methods and techniques. 2 g of the extract and 2 g of the solution of different concentrations of surfactant (SFM) were taken in the preparation of the emulsion. First, SFM was dissolved in water and the extract was added dropwise under constant stirring to prepare an emulsion. When determining the type of emulsion, the turbidity was determined by turbidimetric method, and the rN value was determined by potentiometric method in MBI-6 microscope.

Results. Among solutions of three different types of surfactants from 0.25% to 6%, it was found that emulsions prepared with nonionic and cationic surfactants were not stable. The stability of emulsions obtained with the presence of 6% Tween-80 solution did not exceed 1

minute. When the extract was added to a 0.25% to 6% solution in the presence of the cationic surfactant cetylpyridinium chloride, its stability increased from 0.3 to 1.2 minutes. According to the results, anionic emulsifier had a positive effect on the stability of emulsions. At the same time, the addition of sodium salt of distilled fatty acids (Na-DJK) to the composition of emulsions led to the stabilization of emulsions. Emulsions at a concentration of up to 1% were found to be stable for 4 minutes, at a concentration of 3% for 55 minutes, and at 4% for 1.35 hours, and at 6% for 160 hours. Quality indicators of emulsions prepared from sodium salt of distilled fatty acids with high stability of 4%, 5% and 6% were evaluated.

Table 1

Evaluation of quality indicators of emulsions of extract of carnation flowers in bitter almond oil

Na-DJK salt in the emulsion, in %	Appearance of emulsions	Centrifuge separation time*, minutes	Heat resistance 50°C start of layering, min
4	Homosexual	30	10
5	Homosexual	45	25
6	Homosexual	50	40

*1500 rpm;

Some quality parameters of emulsions prepared from extract of clove flowers in bitter almond oil were studied. According to the obtained results, the appearance of emulsions is homogeneous. It was observed that the stability of the distilled fatty acids increased with the concentration of the sodium salt of the distilled fatty acids when the separation time in the centrifuge was 1500 rpm and the temperature was kept at 50°C.

Emulsions obtained under a microscope belong to type 1 (M/S) emulsion. Emulsion type was determined by dilution method and methylene blue dye solubility. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Microscopic view of 6% DYOK-Na obtained emulsion.

Taking into account that the anionic emulsifier has a positive effect on the stability of emulsions, three different anionic emulsifiers DYOK-Na, Na-SK, Na-ELS salts were used in our next experiments. The particle size of the dispersed phase was calculated by determining the turbidity time using a turbidimeter.

Table 2

Effect of Emulsifier Type and Variation of Oil Ratio in Clove Oil Extract on Disperse Phase Particle Size

(emulsion obtained by mechanical dispersion method at 25oC)

SFM Type	SFM solution: oil extract ratio			
	1: 1	1: 2	1: 3	1: 4

6%	The turbidity of the dispersed system (NTU) and the size of the phase particles, p nm							
	τ	r	τ	r	τ	r	τ	r
Na-ELS	126	42.7	104	40.9	96,4	39.9	78,2	35.9
Na-SK	58,3	33.4	54	32.9	52,9	32.6	51,3	31.8
Na-DJK	51,6	32.1	50,8	32.2	49,4	31.9	48,9	31.6

According to the results, the size of the phase particles of the dispersed system decreases from 42.7 nm to 35.9 nm when the bitter almond oil and SFM solution are taken in a ratio of 1:1 in a 6% emulsion prepared with the presence of Na-ELS. It was observed that the size of the dispersed phase particles of the emulsion obtained from a 6% solution of Na-SK decreased from 33.4 nm to 31.8 nm with increasing oil content. As the most effective emulsifier, Na-DJK salt can be obtained. Because in this case, the size of the phase particles of the dispersed system decreased from 32.1 nm to 31.6 nm.

Conclusions. Surfactants of different nature were added to the extract and emulsions were obtained at different concentrations. It was found that the stability of the emulsions obtained in the presence of Na-DJK salt, which has an anionic character, is relatively high. The size of dispersed phase particles of stable emulsions obtained in the presence of sodium laurylsulfonate, Na-DJK tuzi and sodium stearate was determined by turbidimetric method.

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